

Health Assessment of Flood Protecting Haora Earthen Embankment Through Numerical and Field Experiments

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Abstract Health assessments for vital lifeline infrastructures, such as earthen embankments, are crucial as a substantial population resides downstream of these structures. The Hoara River is one such structure that has played a pivotal role in safeguarding the capital city of Tripura, Agartala, in the northeastern state of India for more than six decades. Since its inception, the embankment has witnessed numerous flood events, consistently demonstrating resilience against the natural hazards of flooding. Over time, the embankment has developed particular critical sections or weak zones attributed to erosion, silting, and thriving human settlement along the periphery of the embankment. This situation mandates meticulous and extensive examination to evaluate the safety and stability of the structure. The present study is a humble attempt in this direction. It evaluates the stability of the embankment, with a specific focus on the impact of infiltration forces resulting from rainfall. The assessment employs a comprehensive approach, including on-site visits, field and laboratory examinations of subsoil properties from boreholes, and numerical analyses using the SEEP/W and SLOPE/W modules of GeoStudio (2018). The results of the study offer crucial insights into the embankment's soil characteristics, revealing a cohesive nature followed by layers of medium to stiff clayey silt and substantial fine to medium silty sand. These findings have significant implications for the maintenance and upkeep of the embankment, providing valuable information for understanding its structural behavior and guiding the formulation of suitable preservation strategies.

Keywords Embankment, North Eastern, Infiltration, GeoStudio.

Introduction

The Haora River, a crucial watercourse in Tripura, flows through Agartala, the capital of the north-eastern state. In 1957, a protective earthen embankment, spanning 5.25 km, was built to shield the Agartala basin from annual floods. Historical records attribute the construction of this embankment to the aftermath of a destructive flood in 1956 (as documented in the technical report of Brahmaputra Board, 2003). Over time, the existing embankment has experienced compaction due to various environmental conditions and regular vehicle movement. However, erosion, human activities, and other factors have disrupted the design section of the earthen flood embankment in numerous places. Locals have reported evidence of seepage during flood situations when a significant rise in standing water level occurred. Animal activities, such as rats creating channels in the flood embankment, have also been noted. Moreover, human activities such as soil extraction from the embankment slope and illegal construction on the slope side, along with upstream soil erosion due to the discharge of entrapped floodwater in Agartala through the embankment, contribute to stability issues in the flood embankment. In the initial phase of the study, two specific locations for exploratory boreholes were identified during a physical site visit, focusing on critical points of the earthen dam. In the subsequent phase, a stability analysis of the flood protection earthen embankment was conducted, considering various significant accidental forces, including conditions induced by rainfall infiltration. The assessment was performed using GeoStudio (2018) software, relying on subsoil physical and engineering parameters.

Study Area

Details of Embankment

The Haora Embankment, stretching over 5.25 km between 23.82°-23.83° North latitudes and 91.26°-91.28° East longitudes, has a crest width of 6.0 m and a side slope ratio of 2 (Horizontal):1 (Vertical). The original design, with a freeboard of 1.2 m to 1.5 m relative to the crest level, aimed to protect the primary Agartala suburb area covering 600 hectares. These design details are extracted from the Technical Report of Brahmaputra Board (2003). In the present context, the suburb area has expanded significantly, accompanied by population growth, intensifying vulnerability to the stability of these flood-protecting embankments. The top width of the Haora embankment is surfaced with brick soling, forming a road on the right bank, while the left bank remains unbanked. For the current study, the earthen flood embankment from Dashamighat to the steel bridge near Pratapgarh (Chainage 0.0 m to 1868 m), spanning a distance of 1.70 km both upstream and downstream, has been selected (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Study area covering 1.7 km stretch of Haora Embankment (Chainage 0.0 m to 1868 m).

Hydrological Details of Haora River

Over the last two decades, observations of flooding reveal a pattern where regular floods occur more than once a year, while severe flooding happens annually. The river Haora, originating from Baramura and flowing westward, navigates steep slopes in hilly terrain before meandering through plains of alluvium, eventually passing through the capital town of Agartala. The river's catchment area within Indian territory covers approximately 488 square kilometers (Bandopadhyay et al., 2013). Due to the hilly terrain in a significant part of the catchment area, heavy rainfall in these regions can trigger sudden flash floods, causing substantial erosion in and around Agartala Town. The Central Water Commission (CWC) has established three flood identification levels: (i) Warning Level at 10.00 m, (ii) Danger Level at 10.70 m, and (iii) Highest Flood Level at 12.40 m.

Subsoil Characterisation

A thorough investigation of the subsoil was conducted to evaluate the characteristics of both the embankment and the underlying soil along a 1.7 km stretch. Two exploratory boreholes, located at chainages 185.0 m and 1680.0 m, were drilled with a diameter of 150 mm and reached a maximum depth of 20 m, considering the crest level of the embankment. Both undisturbed and disturbed soil samples were collected for further analysis in the laboratory. Fig. 2 provides a detailed cross-section of the current earthen embankment at two distinct chainages.

Fig.2. Cross-section profile of Haora Embankment at (a) 185.0 m and (b) 1680.0 m chainages.

Upon examination, three distinct layers consistently emerge, irrespective of the borehole locations. The first layer comprises the filled-up embankment material, characterized by brownish/light desiccated brownish medium to stiff

sandy clayey silt/clayey sandy silt/clayey silt. This layer varies in thickness from the existing ground level (EGL). The second layer consists of a virgin stratum of light to dark greyish soft to medium to stiff/hard clayey silt, displaying fluctuations in thickness. Following this, there is another stratum of brownish to light greyish fine to medium silty sand, occasionally interspersed with localized pockets of light gray soft to medium/stiff clayey silt, extending to the termination depth. Table 1 provides an overview of the physical and engineering properties of the subsoil concerning BH01 (at CH 185.0 m) and BH02 (at CH 1680.0 m).

Table 1. Physical and engineering properties of subsoil related to BH01 and BH02.

Bore Hole No.	Layer (m)	IS Classification	Description of layer	Natural Moisture Content (%)	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Cohesion (T/m ²)	Angle of Internal Friction (°)	Permeability (cm/sec) × 10 ⁻⁴	
								Soaked	Unsoaked
01	0.00-5.00	SM-SC	Light Brownish Clayey Sandy Silt	14.57	1.86	4.60	18.00	4.17	3.92
	5.00-8.00	CH-MH	Light greyish medium to stiff clayey silt	24.71	1.88	4.50	-	-	-
	8.00-20.00 (Pocket layer-10.00 to 13.00m)	SM	Light Brownish fine to medium silty sand (Pocket layer-Light greyish clayey silt)	16.32	2.01	-	35.00	-	-
02	0.00-5.00	SM-SC	Light brownish sandy clayey silt	24.62	1.74	1.50	10.00	2.53	2.69
	5.00-10.00	CH-MH	Dark grey soft clayey silt	32.63	1.79	1.40	-	-	-
	10.00-20.00	SM	Light Brownish fine to medium silty sand	12.79	1.99	-	36.00	-	-

Numerical Modelling

In this study, we attempted to investigate the factor of safety (FoS) associated with a typical embankment constructed using compacted soil, considering various design considerations outlined in IS 7894 (1975) for earthen dam construction. The analysis covered: (i) the long-term stability of the embankment under steady seepage conditions when floodwater levels rise up to the crest and (ii) rapid drawdown conditions following a flood.

During the numerical analysis of the embankment section using GeoStudio (2018), several assumptions were made: a) the material of the embankment section and subsoil layers was assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic, b) Darcy's law was considered valid, c) the embankment was assumed to be in a full discharge condition, and d) failure slip surfaces were assumed to be circular. The numerical analysis conducted using GeoStudio (2018) was based on the limit equilibrium method, specifically utilizing the Morgenstern-Price method (1965). This method ensures both force and moment equilibrium and employs a selected interstice force function. To account for the variation in shear strength due to matric suction, we employed a Modified Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion within the GeoStudio software. Moreover, the analysis employed a half-sine type inter-slice force function for a comprehensive evaluation of the embankment stability under various loading conditions.

Results and Discussion

The compacted embankment currently exists in an unsaturated state. Nevertheless, this state is anticipated to undergo significant alterations following rainfall. To assess stability under these circumstances, analyses are conducted in two stages: Stage 1, which assumes no infiltration, and Stage 2, which accounts for infiltration.

Stability Analysis Under No Infiltration Condition

When the water level is consistently maintained over an extended period, steady seepage occurs, forming seepage lines within the earthen dam section. This situation is particularly crucial for the downstream slope. The stability of the

downstream slope was evaluated using the effective stress method. A scenario is considered critical when steady seepage persists at a constant level in the reservoir for at least one month. The stability analysis of the earthen dam assumes full saturation below the phreatic line. For soil properties above the water table that are partially saturated or unsaturated, we utilize the Fredlund and Xing (1996) method, incorporating soil-specific relationships from the GeoSlope library. The Fredlund and Xing (1996) methodology defines water volume content and unsaturated coefficient of permeability relative to metric suction pressure. To simulate the distribution of initial matric suction and the profile of seepage-induced pore-water pressure within the embankment, we use SEEP/W. Subsequently, stability analyses are conducted with SLOPE/W, relying on the pore-water pressure profiles derived from SEEP/W. The corresponding results are illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig.3. Results of stability analysis under no infiltration condition at chainages (a) 185.0 m and (b) 1680.0 m.

Stability Analysis Under Rainfall Infiltration Condition

Rainfall significantly alters the nature of the embankment. In this study, we assumed an infiltration rate of 9 mm/hour and employed SEEP/W and SLOPE/W for the analysis of infiltration and slope stability in a uniformly compacted embankment. For the SEEP/W analyses, we estimated the hydraulic conductivity and volumetric water content functions using Van Genuchten input parameters ($a = 100$ kPa, $n = 1.5$, and residual water content = 0.05). SEEP/W was then used to simulate the initial distribution of matric suction and the profile of infiltration-induced pore water pressure within the embankment. Subsequently, stability analyses were carried out using SLOPE/W based on the pore water pressure profile obtained from SEEP/W.

Fig.4. Results of stability analysis incorporating rainfall infiltration condition at chainages (a) 185.0 m and (b) 1680.0 m.

Conclusions

This study delves into the critical evaluation of the stability of the existing Haora River flood protection earthen embankment, specifically focusing on the impact of infiltration forces resulting from rainfall. The investigation employs a comprehensive approach, including physical site visits, field and laboratory examinations of subsoil properties from on-site boreholes, and numerical analyses using GeoStudio (2018). The results of this study have significant implications for the maintenance and upkeep of the embankment. The examination unveiled important characteristics of the embankment soil, revealing a cohesive nature followed by a layer of medium to stiff clayey silt, succeeded by a substantial layer of fine to medium silty sand extending to a considerable depth. These insights into the subsurface composition offer valuable information for understanding the structural behavior of the embankment and devising suitable preservation strategies. Furthermore, the numerical analysis indicated a slight reduction in the Factor of Safety (FoS) under infiltration conditions. Additionally, the study anticipates a potential decrease in FoS under seismic loading conditions due to the influence of hydrodynamic pressure. This underscores the need for future in-depth investigations to address and mitigate these challenges.

References

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